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EDITORIAL

Editorial

“Antrope” tem como objectivo oferecer um fórum de investigação, colocado numa óptica interdisciplinar, ao longo do tempo, centrado na História e Arqueologia. Pretendemos contribuir para alicerçar temáticas, que transcendem paradigmas específicos e estanques das várias épocas, nas Ciências Sociais e Humanas e nas Ciências da Terra e da Vida. Desta forma, será proporcionada uma visão mais ampla e completa sobre os processos de evolução ou ruptura das sociedades.

“Antrope” enquanto publicação pretende cumprir todos os requisitos de qualidade estabelecidos para as revistas científicas em formato electrónico, nomeadamente através dos elementos do Conselho de Redacção e dos elementos do Comité de Leitura.

“Antrope” proporciona a divulgação dos seus conteúdos em meio académico, entre especialistas, estudantes e profissionais, funcionando como plataforma entre o meio profissional e o académico, bem como, de ligação, nas temáticas abrangidas, entre a região do Médio Tejo Português, onde se insere, e as outras regiões, quer a nível nacional, quer a nível internacional.

Este número é composto por uma secção uniforme à qual foi dado o título de “O Alto Ribatejo Revisitado” e uma outra, a Sectio, onde se publica informação que está na esfera internacional.

A vertente principal fala-nos dos resultados arqueológicos de trabalhos desenvolvidos nesta região do Médio Tejo Português mais precisamente em Alvaiázere, Mação, Abrantes e Tomar e ainda, o trabalho desenvolvido sobre a base de dados do Centro de Pré-História do Instituto Politécnico de Tomar.

O bloco apelidado de Sectio apresenta versões variadas de outros trabalhos também eles desenvolvidos no âmbito da Arqueologia como os trabalhos implementados em Angola, em Itália, no Brasil, em Espanha e em Portugal.

Com este número 0 pretendemos preencher um espaço que faltava na literatura arqueológica e que, estamos certos, dará os seus frutos a curto prazo.

A informação arqueográfica agora apresentada surge como o facto primário sobre o qual se poderão fazer sínteses no futuro.

Aos leitores e colaboradores caberá dar força a este novo projecto.

Tomar, 2 de Dezembro de 2013

SECTIO

A PRE-HISTORIC ART DATABASE AND ITS RELATIONSHIP WITH A GIS EXPERIMENTNOME

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A Pre-Historic Art Database and its Relationship with a GIS Experiment

Alexandra Figueiredo

RESUMO

Este artigo tem como objetivo apresentar um breve resumo das opções tecnológicas consideradas e desenvolvidas para o estudo e catalogação da arte pré-histórica europeia. Este trabalho foi realizado no âmbito da tese de Mestrado Europeu defendido, na Universidade de Gotland, em 2001.

Este estudo permitiu também o desenvolvimento de um pensamento teórico e uma discussão prática no sentido de propor soluções para a análise e inventário de arte pré-histórica integrado no projeto EuroPreArt – co-financiado pela União Europeia, através do programa Cultura 2000. O inventário e os resultados finais podem ser encontrados na página www.euopreart.net.

Palavras-chave: Euporeu; Arte; Pré-História; SIG; Base de Dados.

ABSTRACT

This article aims to present a short summary of the options considered and technological developments made to the study and cataloging of prehistoric art in Europe. This work was performed under the thesis of European Masters defended in Gotland University, in 2001.

This work was also carried out as theoretical thinking and practical discussion to propose solutions for the study and inventory of prehistoric art EuroPreArt integrated into the project EuroPreArt, co-financed by the European Union, through the Culture 2000 program. The inventory and final results can be found on page www.euopreart.net.

Keywords: European; Art; Pre-Historic; GIS; Database.

1. INTRODUCTION

The “Past Signs and Present Memories. European Prehistoric Art: inventory, contextualisation, preservation and accessibility. – EuroPreArt” project was approved and co-financed by the European Union through the Culture 2000 program.

Its aims were to establish a data-base of European prehistoric art documentation, that included information's about the art, images, maps and bibliography, to publish a guide of good practice and to present the results to the wider public, by building a web-site.

As a further aim, it was intended to contribute to the awareness, among European population, of the diversity and richness of European Prehistoric Art, as the oldest artistic expression of Humankind.

It also aimed to the improvement of methodologies on techniques of inventory, storing data, interdisciplinary, networking and accessibility/diffusion, namely using new information technologies. It was intended the creation of a structure that may ease the introduction and permanent actualisation of a large amount of data, coming from different sources and dates.

The project focused on selected clusters, examples of the diversity of sources, from rock art to mobile art, from Palaeolithic to the Bronze Age, from old stored records to modern field work studies.

Several European partners contributed for it's accomplish, namely Portugal (coordinator of the project by the Institute Polytechnic of Tomar), Sweden, Spain, Italy and Belgium.

After some weeks of discussion, the first guiding lines were established for a experimental database that would support all the information regarding the surveying of pre-historic art that were available in the participant institutions.

It was so created a database that was composed by 5 tables (Bibliography, Eurodb, Institutions, Keywords and Links) and 6 forms (Bibliography, EuroPreArt, Institutions, Keywords, Links and Pixnotes).

With the introduction of data, some little changes were made for the overall improvement of the database, as it's data complexity assumed as relational database with characteristics that decreased to the minimum the entropy and reduction phenomena.

It was also thought that one of the next aims was the relationship of this database with a Geographical Information System.

Fruit of this collaboration and the natural change of ideas, new goals have been established, in a way that a all new project could be designed.

When the new Culture 2000 call for proposals opened, we wished the development of the Europreart project with a new proposal with the title: "Memories looking into the future: inventory, contextualization, preservation and accessibility".

The aims of this new project is in few words: to promote new guidelines and a guide of good practice about the application of information technologies to this kind of heritage; use the socio-economic potential of prehistoric art to develop the regions in witch it is found, the majority of witch is needed; to construct new kinds of web based contents, didactic and scientific; to create a GIS that will be related with the database.

It was purposed to us, the improvement of the database and a development of an experience of the connection of it with a GIS, using a restricted area, as a example of the analytical potentialities that we can achieve with the use of a GIS and its relationship with the information inserted in the database.

The chosen area was the Spanish side of the Guadiana Valley, from where several hundreds of carved rocks, from different periods, were recorded.

With this information we tried to make a set of thematic maps and spatial analysis with the relation of the carved rocks and the kind of landscape where they are inserted.

In the same way, we tried to develop a 3D landscape representation to better understand the space where the carved rocks are.

So, this work will be divided in three parts: the EuroPreArt database, the GIS connection and the importance of using new technologies in archaeology, and the analysis of Rock Art in the Cheles Zone.

2. AIMS AND METHODOLOGY

The purpose of this work is mainly centred in the resolution of a set of problems that arose as the EuroPreArt 2001 project was being accomplished.

These problems were related with the management of the database, the existence or not of certain fields, the relationship between the tables and the data, specific questions regarding the preservation of findings mainly those related with questions of informing the exact location of sites, as others.

The principal aim is to create a user-friendly system that serves two different categories: The researches archaeologists and the common people that have interest for the pre-historic art.

The first, can benefit from a powerful tool for their researches; the second, benefit in the access to a simple information, in an easy and optimised way, because of the inexistence of a demanding for a highly sophisticated support system.

This information can be downloaded to the computer or seen online, having the user the possibility of combine several layers.

Although, the access to some information is forbidden to the general public by a password that is only of the knowledge of the researchers.

Having in account the problems arise from the needs of surveying, analysing, understanding, summarize, manage, store and publish the data regarding to pre-historic art, as well as problems related with the chronological and geographical borders of the project and all that it is bound in it (different styles, cultures, languages, etc), it has been defined as primordial objectives:

1) The development and the improving of the informatics tools for data storing, in way that makes possible its relationship with a GIS, through the:

- Construction of a conceptual model.
- Creation of new relational tables so redundancy could be minimized.
- Construction of a relationship system between tables that coordinates all the information regarding the same archaeological site, through the creation of key fields that allowed the reduction of entropy.

- Introduction of new necessary attribute and change the structure of others, through the introduction of entry masks, validation rules, query's or other relational mechanisms, etc.
- Change of the views structure.
- Elaboration of helps forms for the comprehension of the data introduction and one guide of data entering (Appendix C).

2) The conceptualisation of a archaeological information management geo-referenced system, that served for the research and divulgation of the pre-history artistic heritage, serving as an demonstration example and that could be permanently actualised.

This should be realized through the:

- Gathering and systemisation of all the archaeological data existing for the chosen region – the Guadiana Valley Cheles Zone.
- Treatment of all digital cartography, aerial photo, and other documents, data.
- Introduction of all the carved rocks and its relationship with each chronological moment.
- Natural resources evaluation and relation to local art.
- Crossing of scattered information through overlaying.
- Elaboration of vectorial or raster theme maps.
- Development of spatial analysis maps (visibility, buffers, etc)

The achievement of the first goal assumed the creation of a geo-referenced database so it could allow a easy organization and query of information in a GIS. However, not all the data in the database would be integrated in the GIS, as it is intended that this generates information that answer to a set of practical questions in a rational, easy and fast way.

The second target required the creation of all an archaeological and geographical information base structure supported in a raster and vector format.

The hardware and software choice ad in account the informatics infra-structure already existent in the Institute Polytechnic of Tomar and the easiness in access to all the project partners. In that way, all the applications were developed in a Microsoft Windows® platform, the Data Management System was developed in Microsoft Access 2000®, and the GIS in ESRI ArcView® 3.2 and ArcInfo® 8.1.

The data gathered was the result of surveys done by the Colectivo Barbaron team in the Cheles zone.

The digital cartography used is the result of the digitalisation and vectorisation of the Portuguese Military chart in a 1:25000 scale and a Spanish Military chart in a 1:10000 scale and a topographical survey at a 1:2000 scale.

3. DATABASE

EuroPreArt, just as the majority of the databases has objects, like tables, reports, queries, forms, macros and modules.

This type of relational database management system (RDBMS) allows the user to address a group of complex questions to the tables, being the answers described in a pleasant interface like forms and or reports.

The modelling structure of the data base had in account the area intended to be applied, the types of data and its relevance.

The types of relationships can be created so redundancy can be minimized and the integrity, data validation and safety procedures as well as users types and recovery of data can be assured.

The database EuroPreArt is composed by 141 attributes disposed in 10 tables that link amongst themselves in situations of 1 for 1, 1 to many or many to many, being the second situation the most common.

It was had in account, for the accomplishment of the database, the difficult unification task of such a great variety of records, in terms of type, space, time, artistic objects (ceramic, sculptures, idols, etc.) and archaeological sites with art (Megaliths, Caves, etc.).

This way we intended to divide the database in to two bigger groups:

Rock Art – For all the art represented in rocks, like caves, shelters, megalithic monuments or open-air sites.

Others Finds – To the movable objects with presence or representation of artistic phenomena (sculptures, decorated ceramic vessels, idols, etc.)

The most difficult task to overcome was the field choice as well as the information selection attached to each record. The subjectivity of the concept of art leads us to the difficulty of its definition.

Maybe the first acquaintance of the artistic phenomena is art, in whatever support, author's idea or period.

A word seems to be always associated: feeling.

For the majority of the artists, like Pablo Picasso and Edward Munch, the final result is what the artist creates, but the purpose of his creation is a feeling or a mood. Once an artist creates something, this will represents an emotional state of mind and so, becomes precious to him.

All the concepts that are related with art are so vague and arbitrary, that we would fall in error if we tried to define or simple explain it.

Art as a phenomena that involves the disturbing complexity in its most basic form (its definition), worse when we associate it to archaeology, mainly in the case of pre-history. It is difficult to define what is pre-historic art.

So the EuroPreArt had to obey to a pattern that accepted subjectivity. There is the reason to the creation of a set of subjective memo fields as for example: description, characteristics, observations, etc.

- The tables are organized in way to integrate the whole information regarding the rising of the European Prehistoric Art.

These tables are materialized in views, through the database management system (DBMS) to which it relates, that are not more than forms where in an organized way it is more easily able to introduce, to modify or to query the data, that will be stored as records in the respective attributes of the tables.

Most of the information in a form is coming from underlying records.

The other information is stored in the structure of the form, such as the graphic elements and the support texts.

Like so, the present attributes in the tables are represented in corresponding Views, existing still some forms with help information for the filling of the different fields (Important Instructions and Pictures Notes), a small Start Menu, with connection the all of Views and a subform.

To each attribute of each table there are determined characteristics associated as well as rules, that allow above all the referential integrity of the database.

The main characteristics are:

- The field in the primary table possesses an corresponding primary key that works as a exclusive index.
- The value of each attribute in a tuplo (record) is atomic; that is, it counts only one value.
- We cannot introduce a value in the key field in the related table that doesn't exist in the primary key of the primary table.
- The related fields have the same type of data.
- Some determined fields contain introduction and validation rules that allow the maintenance of the database integrity.

4. CONNECTION TO GEOGRAPHYC INFORMATION SYSTEM

4.1. *The importance of a GIS in Archaeology*

The explosion of interest in GIS over the last 15 years reflects the importance of these applications to the study of space.

This type of archaeological data analysis allows us to achieve important conclusions on men past life, thoughts and activities.

The proceedings of the annual Computers Applications in Archaeology conference (CAA), which saw its first GIS paper in 1986, provides a considerable range of case-studies and theoretical discussions about the importance of the application of GIS in archaeology. (Castleford, 1992; Gaffney, Stancic, 1992; Gaffney, Ostir, Podobnikar, Stancic, 1996; Harris,

Lock, 1996; Kvamme, 1993; Lang, Stead, 1992; Murray, 1995; Robinson, 1993; Roorda, Wiemer, 1992; Ruggles, 1992; Van Leusen, 1993; Verhagen, 1996; Wheatley, 1996; Parcero-Oubiña 1999; Johnson, 1999; Leusen, 1999; Daly, Lock, 1999; Symonds, 1999; Konnie, Westcott, Brandon, 2000).

The archaeological theories that are forming, based in these new mechanisms, contribute for the explanation of determined events and assist to the human being inquiry, such as, for instance, viewshed or cost surface analysis, predictive models, 3D and virtual reality, or the application of more complex data management systems, contributing for a new space perspective metaphor (Wheatley, D.W., 1993, 133-138).

The GIS studies spatial application for the reconstruction of past landscapes and archaeological sites understanding, have two significant contributions: The ancient mind (Renfrew and Zubrow 1994) and Semiotics of Landscape: Archaeology of Mind (Ash, G., 1997), they try to understand what techniques can be used appropriately on archaeological data, and how to implement them efficiently. According to economic theories and their experimental practice, through the understanding of landscape patterns, we can also try to understand mental maps of those who have lived there.

The GIS "is information that describes the distribution of things upon the surface of the earth" (Gillings, M. and Wise, A., 1999, 10), it can explore layers, that with traditional methods could not be explore, and then create economic, political or social models for the archaeological facts explanation, in more than a simple monographical description.

The GIS, will be able, to help the archaeologist to find and understand other paths for the study of the past.

As so, the EuroPreArt database connection to a geographic information system, could leave us to theoretical conclusions, in a more simple, easy and fast way, being able to reach slight knowledge that through simple traditional comment would pass unobserved.

a. The connection to the database EuroPreArt

The GIS is a powerful functionality to visualize, explore, query and analyze spatial data. It is a program that integrates spatial and graphical data with tabular data.

Data can be extracted from documents and typed manually into a GIS table, or a whole report can be captured as scanned text transformed into digital characters, which then can be saved into a variety of word processor formats.

The ArcView possess a Access Database extension, that can use the ODBC (open database connectivity) or SDE specification (new connection dialog), that let us create database themes and see spatial and non-spatial data. The non-spatial data, that is stored in EuroPreArt, has the described spatial data characteristics.

After the extension has been load, we can connect the EuroPreArt database and analyse its data in the GIS.

b. Publishing a GIS on the web

One of the main aims of this project was the intention to reach other people as for example the publication of the data in the web.

This would permit a offering to all, not only of the data that is associated and analysed in the GIS, but also the possibility of interaction in the information association, and its visualization, through downloadable GIS coverages, with added restrictions.

Our first approach to this mater, based on the integration of GIS into the WWW (World Wide Web) in connection with the EuroPreArt database, intends to be the most basic possible launching, the first theoretical strings for the development of a European Rock Art GIS project.

The first prompt would go for the consolidation of a system that unified culturally and informatically the European prehistoric art data. This first data unification is carried through the European Pre-historic Rock Art – “EUROPREART” Database.

This database, besides other information, should contain data to be used in a GIS spatial analysis.

A second look, is going in to the technical factor. The system should be able to support a geographic information system. The used software should be cheap and efficient. That is the reason for the choice of Microsoft Access.

This option was seen as best choice taken in account the users to which it is destined. The easy access of this software (integrated in the Microsoft Office suite), the relationship effectiveness/low-cost and the easiness of its use, allows its embrace by a larger audience.

The user needs only a norm commercial browser to access data. They can get dimamical HTML pages with maps included in them as GIF files, and with information about the site, or sites. This information is saved in the EuroPreArt database, being selected by the search engine and presented in an .Asp format. The links are based also on the "Back" and "Forward" browser buttons. This allows flawless and speed in the navigation without having to request research in the search motor.

The GIS information can be presented in the web, using the ArcIMS extension (for ESRI software like ArcView or ArcInfo), or downloaded and viewed later to save on modem time. The website can have maps, aerial photographs, geographical data, reports, tabular data and computer applications. All of the information can be scaled and zoomed in and out. Several themes can be shown at one time. The ArcIMS have some functionality that can proportionate us measuring, colour tools, coded information, printed out or to put into a presentation application, like PowerPoint. We also have the possibility to construct animated flyovers.

C. Protection problem

When making available the data of a GIS, on the web, we enter a contradictory problem: To be useful, an archaeological data set, must precisely record the location and contents of sites for analyses to work. But can all access this information?

Clandestine approaches can serially harm the integrity of these sites. So we have to consider on one side the space analysis and for other the protection of the carved rocks. Like this, the

only form of over passing this problem is to supply the public space data, through GIS images, without identifying the archaeological places precisely.

The database already counts a process for location data safety. This data type only will be made available for the professional audience and will be obstructed to the general public.

In the GIS, these data is also hidden, being only visible the space analysis images.

5. CASE STUDY: THE CHELES ZONE

All the analysis reports to a total of 574 rocks.

As example of the EuroPreArt connection to a GIS, we choose to consider the Cheles area, in the Guadiana valley, and to develop some thematic maps for the data analysis.

Cheles is located at the Spanish Southwest, close to the Portuguese border. The carved rocks area is bathed by the Guadiana River at West, being prolonged to until the elevations of Cerro del Colmenar, Cerro Miguel and Galacho, to the North and East and to the Friegamuñoz brook (a tributary of the Guadiana) to the South. This whole area occupies 9 hectares approximately. The closest population is located to North, at about 4,8 Km, being denominated by Cheles.

Geologically, this area represents a part of the penny-plain of Solid Hesperic, where devonic, syllabic and ordovicic materials are observed.

The carved rocks were accomplished on the banks of "pizarras silicuas" developed by the devonic sedimentation. The soils are mainly xerorthents with scarce organic material. The poverty of the soil and the climate type generated in this zone gave place to esclerofil vegetation.

Figure 1: The vectorial map of Cheles zone with the location of archaeological rock sites after dam filling.

A. Support informative and digital

The data to integrate the GIS was obtained by the Colectivo Barbaron prehistoric art specialist teams, when of the Guadiana valley rock art surveying and recording, made at request of the Junta de Extremadura.

All the resulting data of this rising was then introduced in EuroPreArt and later transported for ArcView 3.2. and ArcInfo 8.1

The organization of the information, inside of this system, is done by the selection and identification of a group of necessary fields in the conceptual structure of the GIS. Those entities were classified in function of its information and analysis value.

As support of the information base, the area corresponding to the rising of the prehistoric art of Cheles was digitalized, starting from the scale of 1:25 000, leaf no. 474 Monsaraz of the military chart of Portugal, done by the cartographic service of the army.

The selected area is integrated, in the map 1:25000, among the coordinates UTM, datum ED50, area 29, of PC460620 PC490590.

This process had in account 3 different aspects:

- The nature of the entity and the form in which it is made.
- The observation mode, standing out the observation scale, resolution, perspective, among other characteristics.
- And, finally, the objective to which it is meant.

The coverings considered in the digitalisation were, above all: the altimetry - that include 10 meters interleaved lines and the hydrography, with the main courses of water and tributaries in a scale 1:25000, 1:10000 and 1:2000.

For every scale the area is the same.

B. The Technique used in the Rock Art

The observed techniques are the pecked carving, used in the majority of the findings, and the filiform incision. The same techniques that we found in Tejo Valley (Gomes, 1987), at the Zêzere River hydrographical basin (Batata, Gaspar, 2000, 575) and Ocreza, the three sites with open air art in Portugal, closer to the Guadiana River Valley.

There are also some resemblances between the Côa Valley and the Guadiana Rock art, having Foz Côa more variances as the case of scraping and scorch technique (Zilhão, 1997, 22), but mainly by support and localization characteristics (Baptista, 1999, 197).

The filiforme technic can appear in isolated rock as well as associated to the pecked carving, however this association should not be considered as intentional, that is part of a same iconographic message, being due more to the use of the same support type.

This factor demonstrates us the inexistence of a space organization in function of the engraving type, being randomly put upon the images.

On the other hand, it was not observed, until today, any association of the two techniques to the same image.

It becomes well known that, in diachronic terms, all the rocks with juxtaposition of the two techniques, the pecked technique is made upon the filiforme technique.

The pecked carving technique, obtained by a indirect vertical or oblique percussion, delimits the illustration recorded and can also fill out internal spaces, drawing other geometric illustrations most of the time circles, or even zoomorphic.

Collado, (2001) considers two evolution phases, for each type of recording technique, of the art in the area of Cheles.

Filiforme Technique

In the first phase the filiforme technique is characterized by an incision practically invisible, where geometric illustrations are represented with a single continuous line or multiple small lines that repeat in the same sense.

In a second phase, a stronger and visible interruption line is observed from the previous, representing geometric illustrations or representing zoomorphs, these last endowed with great naturalism.

Pecked Carving Technique

The pecked carving oldest phase is characterized by a little deep, done with a circular instrument in an uniform way, vertical and indirect.

The second phase is the most common, it is treated of a pecked carving one deeper, accomplished in a taken care less way, indirect and oblique, adopting a more ellipsoidal morphology.

It is well-known that none these different ways of working the same technique is associate to the other in the same image.

C. *The represented motives*

The motives in the Guadiana River are very diversified, but maintaining stylistic similarities. We can observe different types of anthropomorphs, zoomorphics, meanders, fossetes, circles and others schematic representation.

In is generality they are post-holocenic, having, however, some filiformes that can be attributed to Palaeolithic.

In the different studied areas of the Guadiana river, we observed nuclei that differ amongst themselves for the type of represented motives.

In Cheles it is visible:

- A great amount of zoomorphs (essentially bovid and schematic animals), sometimes the representation of the sex is observed or its association with another circular illustration representing a possible pregnancy.
- Most of these zoomorphs, accomplished by pecked carving, are attributed to the Neolithic or Chalcolithic. However we can consider a zoomorph, accomplished in filiforme, as belonging to the period of Palaeolithic and some, accomplished in the second phase of the filiforme, as belonging to the Age of the Iron.
- The anthropomorphs represented schematically by the pecked technique on the Portuguese side, either in horizontal or vertical surfaces, are rare in the area of Cheles.
- Circles, serpentiformes and others geometric motives, are representations a lot more common, associated sometimes to other reasons and accomplished in the two present techniques in the area of Cheles.

D. Analysis

Being the Cheles rock art surveying and recording works still in development, our efforts have been orientated to the construction a multilayered models and 3d representation working with the available data.

At a research first phase and model conceptualisation we have created several phases in way of reaching our final objectives.

Phases of the project development:

The first phase was exclusively devoted to the EuroPreArt database.

After its execution we proceeded to the data introduction, data from the archaeological sites, compiling spatial data, descriptive and characterizing of each site. With the information organized in the EuroPreArt database we made its connection with the EuroPreArt GIS through the data transportation by ArcInfo SQL Server.

Schema 1 – 1st Project Phase

The second phase is centred in the vectorisation and digitising of a set of spatial data and in the finishing of the connection of the spatial data held in the database (corresponding to the archaeological sites) with the base spatial data (maps, aerial photos, etc).

Schema 2 - 2th project phase

The next phase is the coverage overlaying, the creation and relation of analysis that are not involved with the complete finalization of the fieldworks.

Schema 3 - 3rd project phase

As in the third phase this phase relates more with the development of 3d applications, and cannot demand the ending of the research being made at the field.

Scheme 4 - 4th stage of the projects

We created an animation of the reconstruction of the landscape of the Cheles zone. For that we used the program Metacreation Brice 4 and the Kinetix 3D Studio Max 4.

The final stage would be devoted to the data analysis and interpretation, conjugating it, grouping and relating it in way to get a major amount of possible conclusions.

Scheme 5 - 5th step of the project

Each draped layer can represent different types of data (interpreted or not). The combination of all these 2D information can provide new interpretations of archaeological evidence.

With the combination of 2D and 3D information, we can realize different cognitive levels, not only to understand the landscape, but also understanding the inherent information to each archaeological sites and that was acquired during fieldwork.

6. CONCLUSION

This project, which is still in progress, based in a European co-operative research, was conceived to serve two different categories: The research and the divulgation.

☐ The research - made by those that for a certain way, try to find answers about the past. These can use the EuroPreArt as an inventory and analyse tool.

☐ The divulgation - Directed to the public, with a protection and information aim.

This way the main characteristic should be the simple and fast learning of its use, as well as a easier understanding of the presented information.

Combining with the database, a GIS construction would lead in a sense of benefiting these two objectives. For one turn it would allow the construction of a stronger and stable analysis system, by other side it would make easier the information visualisation in a user-friendly interface.

The easiness of overlaying 2D analysis through different layers with different information allows us to reach some answers to our questions at a simple mouse gesture.

Also the 3D reconstruction of archaeological landscape can provide a fundamental contribution to this project in order that it can help us with the cognitive models.

The presentation of archaeological researches using three dimensions can create the most approximate possible atmosphere to the visual world in its more original form. The objective of the virtual reconstruction of archaeological remaining is to obtain a realistic reproduction in way to get an approach to the real.

This technologies can produce a serial of pedagogical or scientifically benefits, by the appealing and real way that they present themselves and by the possibilities of obtaining a better global understanding of the site and expansion in terms of data visualisation. (Velho, A. e Velho, G. 2000, pp. 489)

In relation to the GIS experimental at the rupestrian art of Cheles, since the fieldwork didn't stopped yet, the four phases have been developed being still in progression the last one.

To the future we pretend not only to do what we planed but also to go further, including to this studies others layers, like geomorphologic and pedagogical analyses, the contemporaneous sites and habitats of this zone, others relational archaeological sites, soil maps, etc.

Also with this work we could measure the difficulties involved in the construction either of a database, either of a GIS, when it concerns pre-history, or in this case, pre-historic art.

What is the relevant information and what are the data that can be discarded?

This simple question, with several consequences in the final work conclusions, doesn't have a definitive and objective answer.

In our case we still cannot say that the approach that we have chosen is the ultimate right one. It is transitory proposal that at this time as much to do with the practical study case zone.

Some doubts that have aroused in this project are still to be answered:

- What is the best approach: the site, the rock, the artefact, the figure, the technique, or the decorative theme?
- Can we do spatial analysis with art?
- At what level and with which consequences?

This is our suggestion, that an approach that goes as particular as possible, like to a figure level, is the one that can have the more enriching results.

It is more coherent for the fulfilling of the database, it is more concise for registration, it has better research possibilities, especially in terms of detecting the connection between figures and space, between figures in a panel or artefact, between figures in different sites.

Mainly this work served to show the potentiality of the database drawn here, and the resources that are opened with its connection to a GIS.

As always, future work means development even if these can somehow not mean progress.

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